

Separatism as the final form of the secession and its influence on the maternal states' future development

Artem Bratko ^{*1 A}; Maksym Filippov ^{2 A}; Sinkevych Serhii ^{3 B}; Iryna Bets ^{4 B}

^{*}Corresponding author: Ph. D. in Military Sciences, Associate Professor of the General Military Disciplines Department, e-mail: bratkoav84@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0001-5503-3318

²PhD in Psychology, Associate Professor of the General Military Disciplines Department, e-mail: maxfeel8895@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0002-0973-5367

³PhD in Pedagogics, Professor of the General Military Disciplines Department, e-mail: sinkevich76@i.ua, ORCID: 0000-0001-5838-2177

⁴PhD in Pedagogics, Associate Professor, e-mail: irchikan79@ukr.net, ORCID: 0000-0001-8241-5493

^A National Academy of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine named after Bohdan Khmelnytskyi, Khmelnytskyi, Ukraine

Received: February 11, 2021 | **Revised:** March 6, 2021 | **Accepted:** March 31, 2021

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4642365

Abstract

In the article the problems with regard to the manifestations of secessionism at the present stage, provide recommendations for combating them have been investigated. The role and place of the world community in counteracting the manifestations of secessionism and the prevention of territorial conflicts on the world scene have been taken into account. It is argued that the primary possible step in resolving conflicts is, firstly, the use of nonviolent measures, political and diplomatic settlement, and the achievement of stability in any state is possible only in the conditions of maintaining the principles of social justice, regardless of territorial identity.

It can be argued that the peculiarities of the origin and development of the separatism centres in the world influence the political and geographical position of the territory. In addition, experts note that the effective counteraction to separatism is to create exactly the conditions under which effective management of disintegration processes is carried out. It seems that the idea of separation loses its popularity over time. In the Donbas, Ukraine deals with hybrid separatism, which is part of the hybrid war of the Russian Federation. According to the researches of the National Institute for Strategic Studies under the President of Ukraine, its basis is political separatism, which is based on the distortion of information, application of special propaganda measures, distortion of the history of Ukraine and myths about a better life in the format of self-proclaimed republics, etc. It is clear that this conflict must end. However, scientists warn against the use of negative experience in resolving such confrontations, especially in Ukraine. It should also be noted that despite the presence of varying levels of ethnicity in secessionist processes in Ukraine, it cannot be considered decisive or fundamental.

Key words: secession, separatism, armed conflict, national security, aggression.

Introduction

The influence of secessionist movements in the modern world is felt by virtually all modern multinational states, namely the desire of national minorities to secede, to create an independent state. This is most often the case in countries where certain disintegration processes are caused by socio-political circumstances. All these processes are undoubtedly potentially dangerous for future conflicts. On one hand, one way of ensuring sovereignty and territorial integrity, as a last

attempt, is to apply even a military component, subject to the principles of the constitution and national law. On the other hand, it should be understood that the use of military forces can help to achieve results in short terms and relieve tension in conflict region, even eliminating manifestations in other regions, but these measures will not eliminate the causes of secessionist movements and are the basis for future conflicts.

Material and methods

Issues devoted to the study and analysis of certain aspects of the secessionist movements (separatism) influence are the subject of scientific searches of leading domestic and foreign specialists. In particular, the concept of “secessionism” and the threats associated with it (F. Popov), the dangers to national interests resulting from separatism (V. Divak), problems of combating separatism (O. Tsebenko, O. Kresina), isolation and research of the political and legal status of unrecognized states (S.

Osipov), study of conditions, means and negative results of conducting a hybrid war (S. Segeda) had been searching by the scientists.

The purpose of this article is to analyse the secessionist and separatist movements, as historical phenomena, influence on the national security, as well as to synthesize possible ways of counteracting the emergence of “quasi-states” and other territories with uncertain legal status.

Results and discussion

There is the cultural and ethnic subdivision, which often can be the reason of secessionist movements. Within a political party or movement, secessionism reflects the desire of the opposition to pursue its own interests and purposes that don't coincide with what is officially recognized and declared.

At the same time, the reasons of secessionism are often associated with a violation of human rights and peoples, national, racial and religious groups (minorities), as well as state interests.

1 Formation of secessionist (separatist) movements and their threat

Thus, secessionist (separatist) movements began to develop actively after the collapse of the USSR. After the proclamation of independence, a number of countries have faced this phenomenon, namely the emergence of “unrecognized states”, for example, the Nagorno-Karabakh Republic, the Pridnestrovian Moldavian Republic (Transnistria), Abkhazia, South Ossetia, and others.

The creation of “unrecognized states” in the post-Soviet area was accompanied by not only peaceful actions and arbitrary local referenda, but also by military operations in the form of armed conflicts between the authorities and illegal armed groups of “unrecognized states” artificially created and supported by the sponsoring state.

Interstate and internal conflicts have no less significant threat in national security. Unlike the threat of illegal activity, trans border crime,

which can be eliminated through the use of law enforcement agencies, the use of military forces in the context of conflicts is not excluded. In all cases, the armed forces have been used in military operations to disarm and eradicate illegal separatist formations.

With the creation of “unrecognized states”, the issue of ensuring international security and stability in a particular region was urgently raised, because illegal trafficking in weapons, ammunition, explosives, drugs, psychotropic substances and precursors, smuggling activity became more active because of the “frozen conflicts”. Without international control over these “newly-formed states”, peace and stability within the country cannot be secured, a favourable environment for the development of terrorism and extremism is created, human and citizen rights violations, repression and abuse against the population in uncontrolled territory occur.

The international community took a firm stance on the creation of “unrecognized states”. That means the territorial integrity and immutability of national borders must prevail over the right to “self-determination”, despite the fact that most of these “neoplasms” have formal signs of statehood; the international community does not recognize these “self-formations”, which in turn does not allow them to act as a separate subject of international relations.

There is no doubt that the global community must take real steps to prevent and counteract

secessionism, neutralize and minimize the risk factors that may provoke territorial conflicts.

Measures aimed at countering secessionism include mutual respect for the sovereignty, equality and territorial integrity of the state; preventing the practice of "double standards"; a comprehensive approach to solving the problem of involving socio-economic, preventive, political, legal and other measures.

Countering the violation of the territorial integrity of States should be ensured, primarily, by the United Nations, which could monitor the situation in different regions and prevent possible ethnic and territorial conflicts. Preventive activities aimed at preservation of the state's territorial integrity should be based on qualitative forecasts that would help to identify the preconditions for the emergence of contradictions in the initial stages. The territorial integrity and inviolability of any state of the world is an integral part of its independence.

Secession can be characterized as a legally issued exit of the territory of the state under the influence of internal forces.

The threat to the security of the state is created not only by the legal or actual secession itself, but also by the presence of terrorist, partisan or military activities associated with its achievement. This thesis divides secessionism into a "military" that threatens security in its various forms, and "peaceful" that does not carry such a threat. There is no doubt that external factors have a great influence on the emergence of secessionist movements, which, in turn, can accelerate the development of this phenomenon. Therefore, peaceful secessionism can be transformed into more radical, even military, depending on the goals of the movement organizers, as well as on the influence of the sponsoring states, which threatens state sovereignty and territorial integrity, destabilizes the socio-political situation of the mother country.

At the same time, the terms "secessionism" and "security" normally co-exist in nonfiction and scientific literature, where it is used to refer to certain movements and situations, as well as in the speeches of political practitioners. Challenges to national and personal security of

all sorts of fighters, terrorists and even peaceful separatists are felt more clearly by the overarching threat that comes from the general concept of the "secessionist movement" as a whole phenomenon.

As a rule, secessionist movements cannot be positioned as a global threat to world security, however, depending on the level of radicalism, aggressive attitudes of these socio-political movements representatives and the inability of the mother country to localize their activities as a result of the assistance of the sponsoring state, they can create regional instability.

Not only secessionism is perceived in this way, but also other concepts that are constructed on the principle of external features similarity of conceptualized phenomena. Therefore, in turn, terrorism didn't position itself as a threat to world security until it was represented by thousands of autonomous organizations scattered across the globe. They pursued local goals, including secessionist ones (such as the Basques, Kurds or Sikhs), but began to form into a common, all-inclusive, socio-political inclination towards radicalism, with characteristic external features, but with different goals and movement.

Thus, secessionism is:

a political movement that aims to form part of a state's territory legally from its composition with the subsequent creation of a new independent state or accession to an existing state;

a socio-political movement aimed at the actual withdrawal of part of the state from its composition by fomenting a local armed conflict (we do not exclude the participation of sponsoring countries) with the subsequent creation of a new state or accession to an existing state.

Secessionism can be represented not only by political parties and public organizations that do not use armed methods of struggle, but also by illegal armed formations. Opposition to the authority of the mother country may not go beyond political battles, but may take the form of open military conflict, be accompanied by mass casualties among civilians and destruction, and cause grave economic, social and

environmental consequences (Popov, 2011, pp. 84-93).

Along with the phenomenon of “secessionism”, there is also a threatening form of it – “separatism”. Separatism in the science of international relations is realized to mean theory, policy, and practice aimed at separating part of the state territory for creating a new independent nation-state. The ideology of separatism is nationalism. Separatism as a phenomenon itself is a rather old phenomenon, the roots of which go back to ancient times.

The reason analysis of separatism gives grounds to claim that its basis is the ethnic, confessional, cultural or economic heterogeneity of the population and the specificity of placement on the territory of the state. The more noticeable the heterogeneity, the greater the likelihood of separatist sentiment in certain regions and, as a consequence, the exacerbation of the ethnopolitical process up to an escalation into ethnopolitical conflict with the elements of separatism. It should be noted that if all types of borders coincide (ethnic, denominational, civilizational, cultural, economic, peculiarities of administrative-territorial division), their barrier role significantly increases. Thus, a peculiar rift in the state creates conflict potential, which quite often, in the absence of adequate internal state policy, becomes a starting point for increasing conflict between different formations (religious, social, ethnic, national, etc.) (Divak, 2010, p. 223).

2 problems of internal and inter-state conflicts

There is no doubt, the difference in the number and strength of parties to the armed conflict of local character is a prerequisite for ceasefire due to the loss of manpower and technology of the armed forces of sovereign states, which, in turn, failed to restore territorial integrity.

Concerning the classification of conflicts, opinions of experts differ. Most researchers believe that inter-state conflicts lose their leadership and internal ones replace them. They are characterized by the emergence of separatism, as extreme forms of nationalism

and religious fundamentalism, terrorism, activation of crime, migration, and they are the beginning of civil war (Panova, 2005, pp. 53-65).

The basis of such conflicts are the problems of economy, social life of the population, the struggle for power, etc., where the state loses its leadership in resolving them. The role and place in the stirring up of internal foreign states' conflicts should be mentioned separately. Such states resolve the interstate contradictions by undermining the country's structure from within by igniting internal conflicts, or they form a global line of conflict (Radetskyi, 2009, p. 225).

With the creation of “unrecognized states”, the issue of ensuring international security and stability in a particular region was urgently raised, as illegal trafficking in weapons, ammunition, explosives, drugs, psychotropic substances and precursors, smuggling activity that became more active because of the “frozen conflicts”. Without international control over these entities, peace and stability within the country cannot be secured, a favourable environment for the development of terrorism and extremism is created, human and citizen rights violations, repression and abuse against the population in uncontrolled territory occur.

The international community has taken a firm stance on the creation of “unrecognized states”. That is the territorial integrity and immutability of national borders must prevail over the right to “self-determination”, despite the fact that most of these “neoplasms” have formal signs of statehood; the international community does not recognize these “self-formation”, which in turn does not allow them to act as a separate subject of international relations.

Political science and law literature has expressed different views on the possibilities of unrecognized states in the international arena. Some authors assume that the fact of non-recognition of a particular entity does not automatically exclude it from the system of international relations. Relations of the world community and individual countries with unrecognized states can successfully develop in areas such as interparliamentary cooperation, cooperation in the field of education, economic integration, production cooperation and others.

All these forms of cooperation are based on regulations – contracts, agreements, and decrees. At the same time, the legal basis for the interaction of unrecognized states with the world community and with each other is formed spontaneously (Osipova, 2011, pp. 124-127).

It is obvious that the behaviour of unrecognized states in the international arena largely depends on their internal characteristics, in particular the degree of democracy in the country, the interests of the political elite, socio-economic indicators. Other researchers believe that it is difficult for states to exist in condition of non-recognition or partial recognition, primarily because of the low level of trust in them by the subjects of international relations. As M. Riegl points out, “most of the unrecognized states are in the position of the exile states, which straitens their economic activity. Unrecognized countries are unable to attract foreign investors, cannot join international organizations (such as the Universal Postal Union or the World Trade Organization), trade in the global market (in consumer goods, military equipment, etc.), receive loans from the International Monetary Fund or the World Bank; their residents are restricted in travelling or representing their "states" in international sports competitions.

In the distant perspective, this situation causes frustration and population decline, emigration of qualified workers and loss of human resources. All of these factors significantly limit the economic activity of these entities. "Given the relationship and interdependence of states in the modern world, limiting state membership in international organizations and the volume of political transactions involving it adversely affect its development (Riegl, 2014, pp. 17-35).

The support factor for the local population is not decisive. The military capability and support of the international community is of particular importance. A striking European example is the events in Croatia. Thus, not only the territorial integrity, but also the signs of nationality in temporarily uncontrolled territories were restored.

Regarding the unifying of East Germany and

West Germany, it should be noted that in West Germany, the living standards of the population were constantly increasing in order for the Germans living in the East Germany to realize that they needed to live according to the same rules and standards that were inherent in the West Germany. Therefore, in the late 1980s, almost 90% of East Germany's population dreamed of unification into a single, independent state.

3 influence of the sponsor state on conflicts

Since 2014, Ukraine has suffered significant destruction from the phenomenon of separatism. Separate spirits are warming up from the outside in almost all border regions of Ukraine - the so-called "Rusyn", "Romanian" variants, etc. The separatism proclamation became the basis for the Russian-Ukrainian armed conflict, which demonstrated the hostility of official Moscow to stability in the region and in the post-Soviet area as a whole. This conflict has resulted in thousands of casualties and billions of losses to the country and is still threatening national and regional security. Russia has occupied the Ukrainian Crimea and sponsors terrorists in the Luhansk and Donetsk regions (Gorbulin, 2015, p. 473).

Considering the issues of secessionist movements that led to the creation of "unrecognized states", it should be noted that none of the above entities would be able to realize their idea of self-determination without a sponsor state. In our case, it is the Russian Federation, which thus implements its international policy in the post-Soviet area by blocking the reorganization of relations between mother states and newly formed entities. In addition, the creation of permanent "frozen conflict", which plays not only a buffer zone but also has the opportunity to influence the socio-political and economic situation of mother states.

There is a probability of the Russian Federation conducting hybrid wars in new forms. The scenarios are similar to Russian / Soviet schemes, but with new changes made possible by modern technologies. They can be arranged:

keen observation of states with a significant

percentage of the ethnic Russian population;

to provoke the moment when the authorities in one of these states begins to discriminate against the Russian population;

to criminalize the actions of the authorities and to sympathize with the Russian Federation over the terrible situation of ethnic Russians in that country;

to urge the authorities of that state to end discrimination and, at the same time, to support ethnic Russians, both through legal means and by means of provocative agents;

to provoke the authorities of that state to open acts against ethnic Russians by taking more restrictive measures;

use Russian agents to escalate the conflict;

to make the authorities of the state choose – to intensify the repressive actions in order to stabilize or give the opportunity to withdraw from the state;

a military invasion under the pretext of “protecting” ethnic Russians from the “aggression” of the authorities of another state.

Based on the facts, it was established that according to the plans of the Russian authorities in the hybrid war an armed confrontation in the territory of Ukraine was to be carried out by an “invasion army”, which included colour irregular detachments, units of fighters, volunteers contracted to participate in the war. The term “invasion army” is defined and supported by individual researchers. In fact, the Russian Regular Army fully maintains and provides for an “invasion army” and at such a level that it can more or less effectively withstand the Ukrainian Armed forces. In terms of Russian propaganda, the “invasion army” is an army of the so-called “Donetsk People’s Republic” and “Luhansk People’s Republic”.

Scientific articles prove that the Russian authorities use the potential of hybrid war in order to avoid responsibility to the international community for its aggression. Although Russia has not officially declared war on Ukraine, the authorities of the Russian Federation are stubbornly lying about their country's involvement in the armed conflict in eastern Ukraine. At the same time, Russian soldiers and officers are fighting against Ukrainian forces

without signs of insignia, shoulder straps, and chevrons. For the same reason, Russia does not consider captured Ukrainian soldiers as prisoners of war, does not fulfil its obligations to use prohibited weapons, and actively uses illegal armed forces for its purposes. A situation arises when the aggressor wages a hybrid war with his hands open (Segeda, Shchipanskyi, 2018, pp. 38-48).

4 Threats to the national security of the modern state

Such sequence of events took place in Georgia, Moldova, and Ukraine in different years. The extreme result is a complete territorial control over a part of the territory, as happened with Crimea; in other cases, partial control of the territory or a “frozen conflict” creation. In these results, Russia gets increased regional dominance and blocks the potential entry of the states into NATO.

The country's security rating was recently published by the Institute for Economics and Peace, which analysed the level of social security in countries, the extent of domestic and international conflicts. Total ranking created based on 23 qualitative indicators from authoritative sources. The rating consists of 163 countries. Indicators were taken into account: the degree of militarization of the society, the level of crime, the number of terrorist acts, the import and export of weapons, corruption, etc. Having analysed the position of Ukraine from 2013 to 2018 in this rating, we can conclude that the direct influence on the level of the state security. It was made by the presence of armed conflict, occupied and temporarily uncontrolled territories: 2013 – 111 place (medium), 2014 – 141 place (low), 2015 – 150 (low), 2016 – 156 (very low), 2017 – 154 (very low), 2018 – 152 (very low). In five years, Ukraine has lost 41 points and is now one of the countries with the lowest safety factor.

The use of information warfare by the Russian Federation to influence other countries and its aggressive actions, including the invasion and annexation of foreign territories, is a growing concern for global security. The Russian Federation is constantly trying to destabilize the situation in other states and interferes with their

internal politics, as it tries to gain more status than regional. To achieve this goal, the Kremlin needs to weaken NATO; however, NATO still adheres to the principle of mutual defence. This is also concerning the United States, as evidenced by the involvement of the US military in European and NATO exercises and training, including in Ukraine. The deployment of strategic bombers and participation in military exercises play an important role in assuring the Allies that they support the US extended deterrence doctrine.

In the context of possible use of military force in the border area to reduce their negative influence on national security, it is necessary to characterize the signs of such threats.

Referring to Lipkan V. and analysing the Russian Federation's actions in the annexation of Crimea, the incitement of separatism and terrorism in eastern Ukraine and the invasion of its territory made it possible to formulate major groups of signs of threats to the national security of the state. These include:

- formation of anti-Ukrainian sentiments of the border area local inhabitants under the military pressure;

- incitement of separatist sentiment among the population of the border guard area based on ethnic minorities;

- a sharp decline in the social standards of border area local inhabitants;

- growing migration in search of better living conditions in the border area of the adjacent state;

- demonstrative build-up of troops near the border and conducting military training;

- reducing the influence and authority of constitutional institutions of power;

- a sharp increase in non-constructive contacts at the level of border guard representatives;

- a sharp increase in the border crossing bypassing the BCPs;

- artificial limitation of border crossing operations;

- active involvement of border guards from the local inhabitants into political processes taking place at the border area;

- conducting intelligence regarding military units and military formations;

- the activation of cross-border crime and its use as a destabilizing component in the border region (Lipkan).

An analysis of the reasons for the loss of control over Crimea and the destabilization of the situation in eastern Ukraine indicates that was made possible by:

- treasonous actions of the Crimean republican state authorities, the Donetsk and Luhansk regional councils, the corresponding bodies of local self-government;

- the unwillingness and inability of the central and regional bodies and the Ministry of Internal Affairs forces, the Security Service and Intelligence agencies to neutralize separatist forces and illegal armed formations;

- the lack of support for the actions of the central state authorities and security structures by a large part of the population of the mentioned regions, etc.

The Kremlin demonstrates a model of inclusive and multilevel warfare involving political, diplomatic, economic, information, social, military, law enforcement and other actions. Identification of that requires unconventional thinking, taking into account the disposition of such a war strategy, greater attention to the hidden phase and the processes that take place in it, understanding the peculiarities of small group actions and the expediency of counteracting negative scenarios in the early stages and law enforcement, gain strategic effect through tactical actions.

The holistic national institute of external and internal aggression deterrence in its present state should lean toward a developed triad of a mentally formed system of non-forceful methods of counteraction, a mobile, compact army, and a coherent territorial defence system in the form of prepared voluntary mobilization resources.

Undoubtedly, non-military structures should be in the centre of the triad of deterrence, since they provide preventive capabilities for the state. They depend on the quality of combat in the non-military plane, as well as the ability to predict the enemy's actions in time. Such non-military defence mechanisms include a developed diplomatic corps and competent

intelligence, specially designed economic and information tools, and a number of other capabilities. The active development of the state's intelligence structures can provide a solution to many problems in the international arena and in the rear of a potential enemy. The training of a new type warfare must necessarily include the development of a means of countering new external and internal military challenges and threats to the state, which must be assessed in the light of world and national experience, the experience of revolutions and armed conflicts all over the world. Information and psychological warfare bodies, cyber-warfare, intelligence and control, robotic systems and other high-tech elements are all things that work in everyday, peaceful life. These forces are the basis of potential for wars of a new type that become more widespread around the world. While forming this potential, it is necessary to take into consideration the importance of taking precautionary measures: the main blow should be made by the so-called "customer" of a possible war, not by the direct aggressor. This pre-emptive blow on the enemy can take many forms – financial, economic, cyber-information, cultural. Because in a new type of war, advances in modern technology can be effectively neutralized by the application of modern social technologies.

We also need to look at the latest history of crises and conflicts in order to understand Ukrainian modern life and appropriate steps forward. Of course, they are in the risk management circle with fast decision-making at all levels (in minutes, not hours), use of latent technologies, rapid deployment and anticipation and ongoing political-military interaction, combined efforts of intelligence agencies.

The war format changing and new components of the new generation war emergence requires the creation of few but competent structures to counteract the enemy's information operations and conduct their own ones. To counter the threat of the destruction of the banking and financial system and the successful conduct of cyber warfare, which no state has previously faced, appropriate units

must be formed. Financial monitoring – financial intelligence – should be established, which should monitor the issue of supporting the anti-government forces financing within Ukraine.

Based on the political issues, the principles of the national economy and information system should be formed and technological potential should be developed through close cooperation with the European countries. Main goals for Ukraine in this case should be to get rid of critical dependence on partners (especially the Russian Federation) in the field of energy resources and key technologies supply, to increase participation in multinational projects, especially in the field of defence.

Thus, today's national security of any country as a whole should be based on international cooperation and the support of international society.

The experience of Ukraine shows that destabilization of the region leads to security problems in Europe as a whole.

Additional confirmation is that there are trans-border and transnational threats in the world. They are: international terrorism; training camps and fortified terrorist bases setting up; international criminals sheltering; illegal weapons and ammunition traffic organization; separatism; organized international cross-border crime; drug distribution; migration; human rights violation; proliferation of mass destruction weapons; poverty; diseases; environmental degradation, etc.

Their detection and recognition are complicated by the fact that most of them are closely related. Yes, terrorism is closely connected with drug and weapon trafficking, organized crime – drug trafficking and illegal migration, conflicts and poverty – migration and others. Given the above-mentioned facts, it was possible to group national threats into six groups:

- socio-economic threats;
- inter-state conflicts;
- internal conflicts;
- means of people mass destruction;
- terrorism;
- transnational organized crime

(Trembovetskyi, Hulevatyi, 2018, pp. 23-29).

Modern world organizations for international conflicts settlement are the UN, OSCE, NATO, EU, CoE and others, as well as leading countries such as the USA, France, Great Britain, Japan, China, Germany and others can be involved in the processes as mediators.

Regarding the role of international security organizations – a regional organization, the Council of Europe – tries to interfere in the resolution of the world conflicts, adopts relevant resolutions, sends observers, and helps the affected countries. Unfortunately, this organization does not have a real instrument of coercion and the prevention of separatism. The only effective and demonstrative step taken by the CoE is that Russia was deprived of voting rights in the Parliamentary Assembly for the annexation of Crimea and military intervention in the East of Ukraine (Tsebenko, 2015, pp. 100-104).

For example, on March 25, 2014, the Congress of the Council of Europe adopted a Declaration, which gave a clear assessment of Russia's actions, defining them as "Russian annexation of Crimea and Sevastopol". It expressed support for the new legitimate power of Ukraine, in particular, in its efforts aimed at strengthening democracy, protecting the rights of Ukrainians and national minorities, and ensuring a constructive dialogue between all political forces. The Declaration, in particular, emphasizes that Crimea already had a rather high level of autonomy within Ukraine, which could be strengthened after consultation with the Ukrainian authorities. The Congress members – representatives of municipal and regional authorities across Europe – emphasized that the so-called referendum in the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and Sevastopol not only did not comply with Ukrainian and international legislation, but was also held without the minimum democratic guarantees inherent in any vote. Thus, the Council of Europe, which is responsible for the development of local democracy in Europe and provides expert support for all local elections in the European area, left no chance with the assertion that the referendum was lawful and that the border between Russia and Ukraine was legitimate.

In addition, the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe adopted a resolution censuring Russia's actions to annex Crimea. "The Assembly strongly censures the Russian military aggression and annexation of Crimea that has taken place over it, which is an international law violation, in particular the provisions of the UN Charter, the OSCE Helsinki Act and the Charter and the basic rules of the Council of Europe", the resolution reads. According to the Assembly, "none of the arguments used by the Russian Federation to justify its actions is not true". The resolution states that the far-right forces did not seize central power in Kyiv, "and there was no immediate threat to the rights of the ethnic Russian-speaking minority in the country, in particular, and especially, in the Crimea". "The Assembly considers the desire of the Crimea separation of the territory of Ukraine and joining the Russian Federation was initiated and provoked by Russian authorities under the cover of military intervention", the document reads.

The UN position is often quite declarative. On fundamental issues, any decision of this organization is vetoed by Russia that is why the UN's activity in combating separatism is ineffective. This organization needs carrying out reforms.

On March 27, 2014, the UN General Assembly Resolution on Supporting the Territorial Integrity of Ukraine was adopted. The document declares non-recognition of the Crimean "referendum" and calls on all states, international organizations and specialized institutions not to recognize any changes in the status of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol. That means based on the above-mentioned referendum all the participants should refrain from any actions or behaviour that may be interpreted as recognizing any change in status.

The OSCE is the most active participant in the settlement, in particular by engaging and sending missions to the conflict regions, but the events in Ukraine and the analysis of the historical past demonstrate that the tools of this organization are ineffective.

NATO is one of the most successful international organizations in the world. The

basic position of the organization is in peaceful conflict resolution and in calling to preserve the integrity and sovereignty of the independent states. Although this organization's actions to resolve conflicts in the world are quite selective. In most world separatist conflicts, this organization does not interfere, particularly in the post-Soviet area.

The settlement of separatist conflict through legal methods makes it possible to reduce the threat of secession and destabilize the political environment. In short perspective, there will obviously be no significant reassessment of the role of separatism in the current system of interstate relations by the global community. In this regard, measures to resolve and prevent

separatist conflicts will not be out of date. International security will depend on the ability of United Nations to come up with a unified and unambiguous approach to the treatment of fundamental rights of ethnic and cultural minorities. At the beginning of new millennium, we have the reason to consider separatism to be one of the greatest and the most controversial problems of the modern world (Tsebenko, 2017, pp. 55-60).

Imposing economic sanctions is one of the most effective methods of combating separatism today. The economic locking of Russia and the separatist regions slowed down the full-rate offensive operation against Ukraine (Kresina, 2014, p. 143).

Conclusions

Thus, we can conclude that the problem of the emergence of "secessionism" phenomenon, on the one hand, the preservation of the territorial integrity of an independent state, on the other hand, remains relevant, unresolved and needs close attention.

Measures aimed at countering secessionism we can include mutual respect for the sovereignty, equality and territorial integrity of the state; preventing the practice of "double standards"; a comprehensive approach to solving the problem of involving socio-economic, preventive, political, legal and other measures.

Countering the violation of the territorial integrity of States should be ensured, firstly, by the United Nations, which could monitor the situation in different regions and prevent possible ethnic and territorial conflicts.

Preventive action aimed at preserving the territorial integrity of states should be based on qualitative forecasts that would help to identify the preconditions for the emergence of contradictions in the initial stages.

In general, methods of combating the manifestation of secessionism and its other forms, including separatism, can be divided into two main

types – violent and non-violent. Violent methods of counteraction include: imprisonment of leaders and activists of anti-state movements, cruel suppression of actions connected with calls for change of territorial structure combined with physical elimination of separatists. Isolation of the problem area (region) from external sources of arms, ammunition and other means that could help to achieve its goal and minimize the influence on the territories of the sponsoring country; destruction of base and training centres of illegal armed formations play a great role in opposition to separatism. Non-violent activities (methods) include granting certain territories (regions) greater powers and authorities (decentralization, autonomy, etc.); financial support for regional elites; state agitation and discredit of separatist leaders; imposing economic sanctions, restrictions, and prohibitions as for the conflict region.

The basic possible step in resolving conflicts is we consider using non-violent measures, political and diplomatic problem solving, and the stability achievement in any state is possible only in the context of maintaining the principles of social justice, regardless of territorial identity.

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